

Synthesis, structure and dielectric properties of giant dielectric $\text{Ti}_{1-x}(\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_2$ ($x=0.01,0.05,0.1$) ceramics

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Abstract

Capacitors have an advantage over batteries with respect to the endurance for charge - discharge cycling and power density. Capacitors can replace Li-ion batteries if energy density can be increased significantly. Use of electric double-layer capacitor (EDLC) is restricted because of the relatively low energy density of EDLC in comparison with lithium ion battery and the leakage of liquid electrolyte from packages. The capacitance density of multi-layered ceramic capacitors (MLCCs) has been increased one million but BaTiO_3 based material exhibits poor temperature or frequency stability. In view of that urgent need, the search for materials with giant permittivity (GP, $\epsilon' = 10^4-10^5$ in a radio frequency range) has been attracting considerable attention for many years due to its very high capacitance and energy density. Very recently, GP with low dielectric loss was reported in (In, Nb) co-doped rutile TiO_2 polycrystalline ceramics [1]. However, it is not economic to use indium oxide due to its high cost. The colossal permittivity is retained with low dielectric loss by replacing indium oxide by cheap and abundant aluminium oxide [2].

Here, we investigated the dielectric properties of $\text{Ti}_{1-x}(\text{Al}_{0.5}\text{Nb}_{0.5})_x\text{O}_2$ [$x=0.01,0.05,0.1$] ceramics prepared by the solid-state method at various calcination and sintering temperatures. Both calcination and sintering temperature have significant effect on phase formation, density, grain size, which are related to dielectric property. The calcination temperature has a great influence on the grain boundary, and that modifies the dielectric property. Impedance spectroscopy was used to explain the mechanism of giant permittivity.

Keywords: Rutile– TiO_2 , Giant dielectric permittivity, Sintering, Impedance spectroscopy

Reference

1. Wanbiao Hu et al. Nature Materials 12,821-826 (2013).
2. Wanbiao Hu et al. Chem. Mater. 27, 4934–4942 (2015).